

Readiness and Sustainability of Selected Higher Education Institutions in Davao City Towards Internationalization

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Abstract

Higher education institutions in the Davao region face a tremendous challenge in terms of internationalization. This study aimed to examine the influence of internationalization readiness on internationalization sustainability among selected higher education institutions in Davao City. Employing a quantitative, non-experimental, predictive-correlational design, the research surveyed 85 college instructors and professors. Findings revealed a high level of internationalization readiness and sustainability, as the college instructors and professors reported. Moreover, a significant strong positive correlation was found between readiness and sustainability. Internationalization readiness was also identified as a significant predictor of internationalization sustainability. These results aligned with Jiangyuan Zhou's Dynamic Systems Theory, which underlines the interconnectedness and influence of various components within educational systems. The study proves that readiness and sustainability function in a dynamic relationship, where readiness is vital in sustaining internationalization endeavours. HEIs, particularly those that have yet to begin their internationalization initiatives, should prioritize enhancing their readiness to ensure long-term sustainability in internationalization efforts. It is suggested that HEIs consider strengthening their international academic and industrial partnerships to increase their opportunities and access to grants and scholarships.

Keywords: *Internationalization readiness, internationalization sustainability, higher education institutions, dynamic systems theory, Philippines.*

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Introduction

As the importance of global interconnectedness has become more widely recognized in economic, political, and social dynamics, the academe's internationalizing function has grown more receptive to interdependence. Internationalization impacts several

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areas of society, including higher education, where there is increased mobility of ideas and people. Consequently, it has posed several challenges to higher education providers worldwide, including their survival. Many educational institutions are working hard to create partnerships and cooperation with regional, international, and even intercontinental colleges in an attempt to benefit from the global trend. With the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) strategies and initiatives geared toward international education all over the world, it is critical to examine their readiness and how their preparation may assist them in sustaining their internationalization efforts. Thus, sustainability must become a prerequisite for organizations' "reason for existence" or *raison d'être* (Bosma, n.d.).

For instance, Japan, like other Asian countries, has acknowledged the necessity of internationalization in higher education. Despite the Japanese government's commitment to internationalization, the number of Korean and Taiwanese students coming to Japan is dropping. Furthermore, the number of Japanese students studying abroad has decreased in recent years and is currently much fewer than in the early 2000s (Kuroda et al., 2018). Despite the Japanese government's help in strengthening their academe's internationalization readiness, they faced difficulties in sustaining their internationalization programs. Under the current and quickly changing conditions in many industrialized nations and the growing rivalry to attract overseas students and researchers, the Japanese institutions' operations that rely on individual competence have reached their internationalization boundaries, as Ohta (2014) insisted.

Kangkha and Mahadi (2017) also confirmed that the lack of English competence is a significant concern for Thai tertiary students towards internationalization. In this context, HEIs that do not use English as a medium of instruction should integrate the English language competency of their students and faculty members in their internationalization readiness to ensure the success of their internationalization sustainability. Internationalization is frequently cited as a means of improving the quality of personnel, academics, and research in underdeveloped nations such as Cambodia, Laos, and Myanmar (Council, 2013; Mathuros, 2013; UNESCO, 2014). Because these nations have a shortage of skilled employees and Ph.D. professors, international collaborations are considered a means of allowing outside information to seep in for staff and lecturers. Furthermore, low faculty wages in these nations do not attract students who have gone to seek graduate degrees overseas, conferring to studies conducted by the Asian Development Bank (ADB, 2012).

In the Philippines, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) issued the Policy Framework on the Internationalization of Philippine Higher Education (CMO 55 s. 2016) to provide guidance and focus on the Philippine higher education sector's internationalization efforts in light of increased globalization and intensifying ASEAN integration. The Philippine government claims that the nation falls behind many of its ASEAN neighbors in terms of generating knowledge builders, researchers, inventors, job creators, solution seekers, and suppliers, all of which are required to operate effectively in a knowledge economy (Sarmiento, 2019). As these variables are part of a Philippine HEIs capacity building and readiness for internationalization, it is critical to construct an efficient intervention to ensure the long-term sustainability of internationalization efforts.

In Davao City, fifty-three (53) universities and colleges are being overseen by CHED as of 2020-2021. Recipients of the Commission on Higher Education's 1st Philippine Higher Education Internationalization Award were given to two HEIs in Davao City. Both institutions highlighted their best practices in internationalization last August 19,

2021, during the 2nd Regional Conference on the Internationalization of HEIs in the Davao region. Dr. Randy A. Tudy, Education Supervisor of CHEDRO-XI, presented the Status of the Implementation of the Internationalization of HEIs in the Davao Region.

Undeniably, many HEIs in the Davao region are still struggling with how to take off on their institutions' internationalization efforts. The result of CHEDRO-XI's study shows that most of the institutions' capacity building and readiness towards internationalization is weak due to a lack of allocated budget for the projects. Hence, sustaining internationalization activities is nearly impossible. Most studies have been directed toward the internationalization efforts of top-ranking state universities and colleges in the Philippines, especially in the National Capital Region (NCR). Because only a few studies have looked into higher education institutions' internationalization readiness and sustainability, the researcher believes it is imperative to dig deeper and examine the relationship between the HEIs' readiness and their road to internationalization sustainability, especially in light of the COVID-19 pandemic's restrictions.

Furthermore, the Dynamic Systems Theory by Jiangyuan Zhou applies directly to the study assessing the influence of readiness on internationalization for sustaining internationalization initiatives among the higher education institutions selected in Davao City. The theory posits that educational institutions are complex systems interacting constantly with both internal and external factors but evolve according to adaptive processes. Readiness in internationalization refers to an adaptive internal mechanism affecting the long-term sustainability of an institution. Zhou's theory implies that readiness and sustainability are linked: institutions must constantly adapt to changes, challenges, and opportunities across various places in the world. By learning this interplay, the study falls within the framework that the theory puts forward: such systems' sustainability is not static but a result of ongoing interactions and readjustments within a changing educational landscape. Because of this interplay, it is right to use Zhou's theory to work out a grip on readiness' influence on the sustainability of internationalization initiatives.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to examine whether readiness in internationalization is a significant predictor on sustainability in internationalization of the selected higher education institutions in Davao City throughout the academic year 2021-2022. Specifically, this study sought to provide empirical findings to the following objectives:

1. To ascertain the level of readiness of selected higher education institutions in Davao City towards internationalization as perceived by faculty members in terms of academic standards and quality, structure and staff, budget and implementation, facilities and support system, international and intercultural understanding/networking.
2. To ascertain the level of sustainability of selected higher education institutions in Davao City towards internationalization as perceived by the faculty members in terms of curriculum and instruction, extra-curricular activities, research and scholarly activities, program mobility, and student and faculty mobility.
3. To determine whether there is a significant positive correlation between readiness in internationalization and sustainability in internationalization of the selected higher education institutions in Davao City.

4. To examine whether readiness in internationalization is a significant predictor of sustainability in internationalization of the selected higher education institutions in Davao City.

Materials and Methods

The research employed a quantitative non-experimental design utilizing a predictive-correlational approach. The predictive-correlational approach allowed the researcher to explore internationalization readiness and the sustainability of internationalization among selected higher education institutions. The study was conducted within three higher education institutions (HEIs) that are members of the Davao Association of Catholic Schools, Inc.

The research respondents comprised 85 faculty members from the three selected HEIs, with 72 participants from HEI A, six from HEI B, and seven from HEI C. These respondents were randomly selected based on specific criteria: they were male, female, or LGBTQ+ members of legal age, employed as faculty in an HEI recognized by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Davao Association of Catholic Schools, Inc., and were teaching during the academic year 2021-2022. All respondents voluntarily agreed to partake in the study. The respondent selection ensured a diverse representation of faculty members, aligning with the study's intent of understanding internationalization efforts.

The researcher utilized a 50-item adapted, validated, and pilot-tested survey tool to gather data. The instrument to assess internationalization readiness was adapted from studies by Dimasindel and Salam (2018) and Balagtas et al. (2013), which yielded a Cronbach alpha of 0.938. To measure internationalization sustainability, the tool was adapted from CHEDRO-XI (2021) and yielded a Cronbach alpha of 0.941. The overall reliability score was excellent, with a Cronbach alpha of 0.966. Data collection followed a systematic process, beginning with obtaining ethical clearance from the Holy Cross of Davao College Research Ethics Committee dated January 4, 2022, securing necessary permissions, administering and collecting the informed consent forms and then the survey questionnaires. The gathered data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including mean, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient, and simple linear regression.

Results

The first research objective of this study was to ascertain the level of readiness of selected higher education institutions in Davao City towards internationalization as perceived by faculty members in terms of academic standards and quality, structure and staff, budget and implementation, facilities and support system, international and intercultural understanding/networking. Shown in Table 1 is the answer to this objective.

Table 1. Level of Readiness of Selected Higher Education Institutions in Davao City Towards Internationalization as Perceived by Faculty Members

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Level
Academic Standards and Quality	3.99	High
Structure and Staff	4.16	High
Budget and Implementation	3.90	High
Facilities and Support System	3.77	High
International and Intercultural Understanding/Networking	3.83	High
Overall	3.93	High

The level of readiness of selected higher education institutions in Davao City towards internationalization, as perceived by faculty members, is reflected in the following means and descriptive levels: *academic standards and quality* has a mean of 3.99 with a high descriptive level, *structure and staff* has a mean of 4.16 with a high descriptive level, *budget and implementation* has a mean of 3.90 with a high descriptive level, *facilities and support system* has a mean of 3.77 with a high descriptive level, and *international and intercultural understanding/ networking* has a mean of 3.93 with a high descriptive level. The overall readiness toward internationalization mean is 3.93, with a high descriptive level.

In addition, the second research objective of this study was to ascertain the level of sustainability of selected higher education institutions in Davao City towards internationalization as perceived by the faculty members in terms of curriculum and instruction, extra-curricular activities, research and scholarly activities, program mobility, and student and faculty mobility. Shown in Table 2 is the answer to this objective.

Table 2. Level of Sustainability of Selected Higher Education Institutions in Davao City Towards Internationalization as Perceived by Faculty Members

Domains	Mean	Descriptive Level
Curriculum and Instruction	3.81	High
Extra-Curricular Activities	3.61	High
Research and Scholarly Activities	3.82	High
Program Mobility	3.48	High
Student and Faculty Mobility	3.42	High
Overall	3.63	High

The level of sustainability of internationalization initiatives in selected higher education institutions in Davao City, as perceived by faculty members, is reflected in the following means and descriptive levels: *curriculum and instruction* has a mean of 3.81 with a high descriptive level, *extra-curricular activities* has a mean of 3.61 with a high descriptive level, *research and scholarly activities* has a mean of 3.82 with a high descriptive level, *program mobility* has a mean of 3.48 with a high descriptive level, and *student and faculty mobility* has a mean of 3.63 with a high descriptive level. The overall sustainability mean is 3.61 with a high descriptive level.

Moreover, the third objective of this study is to determine whether there is a significant positive correlation between readiness in internationalization and sustainability in internationalization of the selected higher education institutions in Davao City. Shown in Table 3 is the answer to this objective.

Table 3. Correlation Between Readiness and Sustainability Toward Internationalization

Variables	r	p-value	Decision on H_01	Interpretation
Readiness and Sustainability Toward Internationalization	.824	.000	Reject	Significant Strong Positive Correlation

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The bivariate correlation between readiness and sustainability toward internationalization among selected higher education institutions in Davao City shows an r value of .824, indicating a significant strong positive correlation. The p-value is .000, which leads to the decision to reject the first null hypothesis (H_01).

Furthermore, the fourth objective of this study is to examine whether readiness for internationalization is a significant predictor of sustainability in the internationalization of the selected higher education institutions in Davao City. Shown in Table 4 is the answer to this objective. The analysis shows that readiness has a significant positive influence on the sustainability of internationalization efforts among selected higher education institutions.

Table 4. Influence of Readiness on the Sustainability in Internationalization Among Selected Higher Education Institutions in Davao City

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	-.493	.313		-1.573	.120
Readiness (<i>Predictor</i>) and Sustainability (<i>Dependent</i>)	1.048	.079	.824	13.253	.000

Note: R = .824; R² = .679; F-value = 175.642; p-value = .000

The unstandardized coefficient (B) is 1.048, with a standard error of .079. The standardized coefficient (Beta) is .824, with a t value of 13.253 and a significance level of .000. The overall model reveals an R value of .824 and an R² of .679, indicating that 67.9% of the variance in sustainability is explained by readiness. The model's F-value is 175.642, with a p-value of .000, confirming the model's significance which leads to the decision to reject the second null hypothesis (H_02).

Discussion

The findings have reflected a high level of internationalization readiness among Davao City college teachers, in line with previous research by Dimasindel and Salam (2018), who noted that institutions of higher education in Southern Philippines are gradually building the structures and networks necessary to achieve international education standards. Readiness, therefore is important in this scenario since it tells of something solid established as a foundation for future international collaborations and standards. The sustainability of internationalisation activities, from the teachers' point of view, is high. This is consistent with the observation of Cinches et al. in their 2017 study that even as many efforts in internationalization at Philippine higher education are

institutionally funded, achieving financial self-sufficiency is envisioned in the long run. The strong positive association found between readiness and sustainability justifies building up institutional capacity for internationalization efforts to gain sustainability over a period of time. Truly, the development of preparedness and capability should be nurtured in order to sustain the sustainability reforms alongside education initiatives (Stringer, 2013, as cited by Sahlin & Styf, 2021).

Significantly, this finding of the study depicts the fact that preparedness for internationalization affects the sustainability of internationalization initiatives in higher education institutions operating in Davao City. Thus, preparedness is important to ensure long-term international academic nexus. Readiness at the institutional level is more likely to sustain internationalization over a long period. Earlier, readiness has come out as critical to the sustainability of competitiveness in an increasingly globalized academy. True enough, being prepared for internationalization is a crucial element for institutions aiming to stay competitive in a globalized environment (Chen & Lo, 2013; Deardorff & Jones, 2012; Knight, 2012; Seeber et al., 2016; Urban & Palmer, 2014; Will, 2015). Alvira-Watson (2019) rightly suggested that administrators are institutional designers who must identify needs and resources and develop strategies matched to international goals. If there is inadequate preparedness, these efforts are tough to sustain because the institutions might not be well-poised to meet the fast-changing demands of internationalization.

Conclusion

The results indicate a high level of readiness and sustainability in efforts by colleges to internationalize higher education. Moreover, the two variables correlate strongly and positively at a significant level, indicating that prepared institutions for internationalization are likely to enhance their potential for sustainability over time. More importantly, readiness for internationalization is said to be one of the key factors for the sustainability of such efforts, with the belief that thorough preparation is required for long-term sustainability in cross-border education strategies.

Higher education institutions are also urged to enhance their preparedness for internationalization by enhancing faculty development, infrastructure, and institutional policies. Further action will strengthen the sustainability of internationalization initiatives. In particular, institutions should further investigate and make virtual internationalization a priority by incorporating virtual opportunities for cross-border learning and making it easier for individuals to collaborate globally through digital platforms. Further research could confirm particular readiness and sustainability factors and examine other perspectives that include the views of students and administrators to more fully understand the nature of internationalization in higher education contexts. Its impact on readiness and sustainability, therefore, comes into play, especially in the wake of increasing relevance for virtual internationalization today. This should also be given importance in response to the growing demands of internationalization.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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